

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF EXEMPLIFICATION OF THE TARGETED LEVEL OF ACQUISITION OF LIFE CONTENT DURING THE STUDENT PERIOD

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Abstract. The article focuses on the psychological aspects of determining the meaning of life during the student period. First of all, theoretical approaches to the content and characteristics of the process of determining the vital content are reflected in it. At the same time, in order to empirically study the manifestation of life content during the student period, research work was conducted and conclusions were formed.

Key words: personality, student personality, value, life purpose, leadership activity, "I" image, self-awareness, self-evaluation, success criteria, life views, behavior, life goals, life process, life satisfaction, locus of control, control of life.

Аннотация. Мақолада талабалик даврида ҳаёти мазмунни мўлжалга олишнинг психологик жиҳатларига эътибор қаратилган. Унда даставвал ҳаётий мазмунни мўлжалга олиш жараёнининг мазмуни ва хусусиятлари борасидаги назарий ёндашувлар ўз аксини топган. Шунинг билан бирга талабалик даврида ҳаётий мазмунни мўлжалга олишни намоён бўлишини эмпирик ўрганиш мақсадида тадқиқот иш олиб борилиб, хулосалар шакллантирилган.

Калит сўзлар: шахс, талаба шахси, қадрият, ҳаётий мазмуни мўлжалга олиш, етакчи фаолият, "Мен" образи, ўзини ўзи англаш, ўзини ўзи баҳолаш, муваффақият мезонлари, ҳаётий қарашлар, хулқ-атвор, ҳаётий мақсадлар, ҳаёт жараёни, ҳаётдан қониққанлик, локус назорат, ҳаётни бошқариш.

Аннотация. Статья посвящена психологическим аспектам стремления к смыслу жизни в студенческие годы. В ней отражены теоретические подходы к содержанию и особенностям процесса первоначального стремления к жизненному содержанию. Одновременно было проведено исследование и сформированы выводы с целью эмпирического изучения проявления концентрации жизненного содержания во времени студента.

Ключевые слова: личность, личность студента, ценность, смысл жизни, ведущая деятельность, образ "я", самосознание, самооценка,

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критерии успеха, жизненные взгляды, поведение, жизненные цели, жизненный процесс, удовлетворенность жизнью, локус контроля, управление жизнью.

According to the recognition of a number of researchers who have studied the student period, the unique characteristics of this age period are the unity and integrity of the psychological changes that occur at this age. At this age, in addition to the transition of leading activities to educational and professional activities, the formation of intersystemic values takes place in a person, and a system of normative values is formed. At this point, changes are observed in the system of self-awareness, the image of "I" gains great importance. Self-assessment criteria and levels will change. Young people become active and make plans for the future.

From the changes recognized above, it is possible to consider the student age as a period when a person is actively engaged in building not only a professional, but also a personal life strategy (path) in a wider scope. One of the success criteria of such activities can be a high level of life satisfaction.

The purpose of our research is to study the nature of the relationship between the orientation of the meaning of life and the ways of overcoming difficult life situations. In connection with this, we solved the following empirical tasks:

- to determine the degree of formation of life content orientation in students;
- to determine the inherent characteristics of students' behavior;
- researching the level of life satisfaction among students;
- to study the relationship between the level of life satisfaction, the characteristics of the orientation of the meaning of life and the optimal ways to overcome difficult life situations [2].

A connection between the general indicator of life meaning orientation and active ways of overcoming difficult life situations was determined. In this way, a person who can set goals related to self-expression and strives to find the meaning of his personal life, confident in himself, overcomes the difficulties and problems that arise with his own strength, knowledge, tend to actively change based on skills and competence. In our study, it was determined that the level of satisfaction with life of students is related to the general indicator of life content orientation. We can emphasize that when the subject enriches his life with content, his level of satisfaction with life increases in general. Indirect

manipulative way was observed in our study that there is a reciprocal correlation between the slow way of avoidance and life satisfaction [1].

Thus, a person who mostly uses slow and manipulative ways to overcome difficult life situations gets less satisfaction from life. This can be explained by the fact that, on the one hand, the implementation of ineffective ways of life, especially relying on his subjective point of view, does not lead to success in life, and on the other hand, when a person is not satisfied with his personal life, he does not consider it important to show his personal activity.

A positive correlation was observed between manipulative forms representing an indirect path, aggressive forms with an asocial path, and avoidance forms representing slow paths [1].

We assume that in this way a unique strategic model of behavior in difficult situations will be embodied before our eyes. For example, if the subject shows manipulative and evasive behavior when faced with difficult life situations, he relies on defensive aggression as the importance of the situation increases.

In order to study the formation of life satisfaction during the student period, we used the methodology of "planned acquisition of the content of life" in the test group. The main goal of conducting the methodology is to determine whether the understanding of life content during the student period is a factor that determines their satisfaction with life. The research methodology was conducted in a group of testers, and the results were analyzed in terms of quantity and quality. The results of the quantitative analysis were presented in tables and diagrams.

Table 1

The level of awareness of life content during the student period (on average value)

No	Indicators	1st course	3rd course
1	Goals in life	19,6	21,9
2	Life process or interest and emotional fulfillment of life	18,7	19,5
3	Life satisfaction or self-renewal	17,3	18,9
4	Locus of control-I (I am the master of life)	20,6	21,3
5	Locus of control – life or management of life	21,7	22,6

According to the results of the table, we can see that the goals in life in the test group were $M=19.6$ and $M=21.9$. It is known that the goal is the image of the final result of human activity and the fulfillment of needs. It is worth noting that it represents the presence or absence of goals for the future life, it is distinguished by giving meaning to life. It also shows the students that they are goal-oriented and that they are living with the present or the past.

If we look at the results of students on the scale of life process or interest and emotional fulfillment of life, $M=18.7$ and $M=19.5$. The essence of this scale is consistent with the popular theory that the only meaning in life is to live. This indicator shows whether the examinee considers his life process to be interesting, emotionally complete and meaningful. According to him, the significance of indicators in the test subjects shows that they are a person living with today. Also, in some places, it shows that a person is not satisfied with his life today, but the memories of the past and the direction of the future can have meaning for him.

Life effectiveness or self-recovery satisfaction is $M=17.3$ and $M=18.9$ in the test group. According to him, it shows that satisfaction with the result of life in the group of test subjects is at a significant level. This scale reflects the assessment of the past part of life, that is, it shows how effectively and meaningfully the life was spent. At this point, these indicators reflect the fact that the past life was good and the memories in it give meaning to the rest of the person's life.

In personality psychology, it is called locus of control when a person assigns responsibility for what happens to him to external factors or to himself. This concept was introduced by DJ Rotter. If a person has an internal locus of control, such people are called internals. He feels like the creator of his life. Internals are not very influenced by others, if they feel an attempt to control them, they show their resistance to it. They work better in isolation than under supervision and have a hard time forgiving the lack of personal freedom.

In the group of students, we can see that the locus of control-I (I am the master of life) was $M=20.6$ and $M=21.3$. This shows that they have a vision of themselves as a strong person and enough freedom to make decisions, to build life based on their goals and visions. If a person thinks that what is happening to him is the result of external forces beyond his control, they are called external, he is inclined to accept all these events.

Even if they do not occupy high peaks in life creativity like internals, they cannot solve complex problems. Externals adhere to the law of conformity, are

influenced and pressured by others and work better together with people than alone. They find it difficult to organize their activities, they mainly take external demand into account when planning.

Locus of control is inextricably linked with how a person builds relationships with others. As a rule, internals are more popular in a more confident group and more patient than externals. Interns have an active attitude towards their own health: they know their health better, take care of themselves and seek preventive care more often. Externality is characterized by a depressed mood and concern for health.

For many years, the locus of control was considered to be a stable description of a person that is preserved for a long time and related to his achievements and failures in all areas of life, health, education, work, family, friends. But later, it is determined that the locus of control can change depending on the real possibilities of influencing a person's life. But whatever it is, it is more important that a person be more realistic in assessing what is happening. Accordingly, we can see that Locus was $M=21.7$ and $M=22.6$ in the group of control-life or life control subjects. According to him, it is determined by the presence of the opinion that a person has the right to control his life, to make an independent decision and to have the opportunity to implement it.

According to the results of the above-mentioned empirical analysis, the formation of the competence of determining the meaning of life during the student period depends on the level of their knowledge, skills and competences. At the same time, the increase in their views, thoughts and ideas about life can be one of the important factors in the development of life values. From this point of view, the following conclusions can be drawn regarding the development of the intended acquisition of the meaning of life during the student period:

- age differences are clearly visible in the formation of life values during the student period;
- the manifestation of life values in the personality of the student is determined in many cases by the understanding of life content and the level of adaptation to social life relations;
- the student's understanding of life content is a factor that strengthens their life values.

References:

1. Джидарьян И.А., Антонова Е.В. "Проблема общей удовлетворенности жизнью: теоретическое и эмпирическое исследование" Сознание личности в кризисном обществе. М. Институт психологии РАН, 1995, ст. 76-94

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2.Формирование личности в переходный период от подросткового к юношескому возрасту: ред. И.В.Дубровина. –М.: Педагогика, 1987. -173 ст.

